

AREA EFFICIENT 3.3GHZ PHASE LOCKED LOOP WITH FOUR MULTIPLE OUTPUT USING 45NM VLSI TECHNOLOGY

Ms. Ujwala A. Belorkar¹ and Dr. S.A.Ladhake²

¹Department of electronics & telecommunication ,Hanuman Vyayam Prasarak Mandal's College of Engineering & Technology, Amravati. Maharashtra.

ujwalabelorkar@rediffmail.com

²Sipana's College of Engineering & Technology, Amravati, Maharashtra.

sladhake@yahoo.co.in

Abstract

This paper present area efficient layout designs for 3.3GigaHertz (GHz) Phase Locked loop (PLL) with four multiple output. Effort has been taken to design Low Power Phase locked loop with multiple output, using VLSI technology. VLSI Technology includes process design, trends, chip fabrication, real circuit parameters, circuit design, electrical characteristics, configuration building blocks, switching circuitry, translation onto silicon, CAD and practical experience in layout design. The proposed PLL is designed using 45 nm CMOS/VLSI technology with microwind 3.1. This software allows designing and simulating an integrated circuit at physical description level. The main novelties related to the 45 nm technology are the high-k gate oxide, metal gate and very low-k interconnect dielectric. The effective gate length required for 45 nm technology is 25nm. Low Power (0.211miliwatt) phase locked loop with four multiple outputs as PLL8x, PLL4x, PLL2x, & PLL1x of 3.3 GHz, 1.65 GHz, 0.825 GHz, and 0.412 GHz respectively is obtained using 45 nm VLSI technology.

Index Terms : phase-locked loop (PLL), high performance voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO), 45nm technology, multiple outputs, low power.

1. INTRODUCTION

Power has become one of the most important paradigms of design convergence for multi gigahertz communication systems such as optical data links, wireless products, microprocessor & ASIC/SOC designs. The current leading-edge technologies (such as low bit-rate video and cellular communications) already provide the end-users a certain amount of processing power and portability. This trend is expected to continue, with very important implications on VLSI and systems design. One of the most important characteristics of information services is their increasing need for very high processing power and bandwidth (in order to handle real-time video, for example). The other important characteristic is that the information services tend to become more and more personalized (as opposed to collective services such as broadcasting), which means that the devices must be more intelligent to answer individual demands, and at the same time they must be portable to allow more flexibility/mobility.

Since the multiple outputs Phase Locked Loop (PLL) provides multiple clock generation, it is to be needed to design PLL with multiple output for modern communication Engineering applications with low power, high stability and low jitter.

This paper introduces a design aspect for layout design of low power PLL with four multiple output using VLSI technology.

PLL is widely applied for different purposes in various domains such as communication and instrumentation. Phase locked loop can be used to maintain a well-defined phase, and hence frequency relation between two independent signal sources [2].

The proposed PLL is a feed back system composed of three elements: a phase detector, a loop filter and a high performance voltage controlled oscillator (VCO).

Reported work describes the use of VLSI technology to design optimum layout for Low Power, High performance phase locked loop with multiple output. The design process, at various levels, is usually evolutionary in nature. It starts with a given set of requirement. When the requirements are not met, the design has to be improved. More simplified view of the VLSI technology consists of various representations, abstractions of design, logic circuits, CMOS circuits and physical layout.

Here for the design, microwind 3.1 VLSI Backend software is used. This software allows designing and simulating an integrated circuit at physical description level. The proposed PLL is designed using 45 nm CMOS/VLSI technology in microwind 3.1 software, which in turn offers high speed performance at low power [1].

The main novelties related to the 45 nm technology are the high-k gate oxide, metal gate and very low-k interconnect dielectric [1]. The effective gate length required for 45 nm technology is 25nm. Some of the key features of 45 nm technologies from various providers like TSMC, Fujitsu, and Intel are as given in table-I below.

TABLE I
KEY FEATURES OF 45 NM TECHNOLOGY

Parameter	Value
VDD (V)	0.85-1.2 V.
Ioff N (nA/um)	5-100
Ioff P (nA/um)	5-100
Gate dielectric	SiON, HfO ₂
No. of metal layers	6-10

Compared to 65-nm technology, 45 nm technology must offer:

- 1) 30% increases in switching performance
- 2) 30 % reduction in Power consumption
- 3) 2 times higher density

- 4) 2 times reduction of the leakage between source and drain and through the gate oxide [1].

Considering the advantage of 45 nm technologies over 90 nm & 65 nm technologies, the proposed work is done with 45 nm technologies. Power consumption is a limiting factor in VLSI integration for portable applications. The resulting heat dissipation also limits the feasible packaging and performance of the VLSI chip. Since the dynamic power dissipation in synchronous digital integrated circuit is determined by CV^2f , reducing the supply voltage is an effective way to reduce power consumption of the modern electronic systems [2]. As the supply voltage scales down with the technology, any power supply noise on power and ground level affects the analog circuit performance more than before. This power supply noise has a direct effect on the voltage controller oscillator (VCO) output frequency of PLL which is proportional to the control voltage from the charge pump.

Following steps are involved to obtain the proposed design. Every step of design follows the design flow of microwind 3.1 software.

2. PROPOSED PHASE LOCKED LOOP DESIGN

Until DSP technology is capable of directly processing and generating the RF signals used to transmit wireless data, traditional RF engineering will remain a fundamental part of wireless communication systems design. As it stands, wireless transceivers must still be able to generate a wide range of frequencies in order to upconvert the outgoing data for transmission and downconvert the received signal for processing. Monolithic phase locked loops have been used for clock-&-data recovery in communication system, clock generation and distribution in microprocessor and frequency synthesis in wireless application. [3].

A proposed PLL is a feedback system composed of three elements: a phase detector, a loop filter and a high performance voltage controlled oscillator (VCO). To obtain the layout of proposed PLL, CMOS circuit of each element of proposed PLL is converted into physical layout using lambda based rules of microwind 3.1 software. After cascading the layout of each element, final layout is obtained. This paper particularly focuses on analysis and design of phase-locked loop with low power consumption using VLSI technology.

3. DESIGN OF PHASE DETECTOR & FILTER

The phase detector of the PLL is the XOR gate [3]. The XOR gate output produces a regular square oscillation V_{PD} when the clock input circuit and signal input $clkIn$ have one quarter of period shift (90° or $\pi/2$).

Average value Of VPD

Fig.2.2.1 The XOR Phase detector at work

For other angles, the output is no more regular. As shown in fig-1, at initialization, the average value of XOR output V_{PD} is close to 0. When the phase between clkDiv and ClkIn is around $\pi/2$, V_{PD} is $VDD/2$, then it increases to VDD .

The gain of the phase detector is the ratio between V_{PD} and $\Delta\phi$. When the phase between clkDiv and ClkIn is around $\pi/2$, V_{PD} is $VDD/2$, then it increases to VDD . The gain of the phase detector is the ratio between V_{PD} and $\Delta\phi$. When the phase difference is larger than π , the slope sign is negative until 2π . When locked, the phase difference should be close to $\pi/2$.

The XOR gate output produces a regular square oscillation VPD when the clkIn and the signal clkdiv have one quarter of period shift (90 or $\pi/2$). For other angles output is not regular. Following fig - 2 shows CMOS circuit for XOR gate.

Fig. 2 CMOS circuit for XOR Gate

The low-pass filter smooth out the abrupt control inputs from the charge pump. Since initially the oscillator may be far from the reference frequency, practical phase detectors may also respond to frequency differences, so as to increase the lock-in range of allowable inputs. The low pass filter for proposed PLL is designed using virtual resistance of 1000 ohm with capacitor of 2 Pico farad.

4. DESIGN OF THE VOLTAGE CONTROLLED OSCILLATOR AND MULTIPLE OUTPUT UNIT

The VCO is the most important functional unit in the PLL. Its output frequency determines the effectiveness of PLL. In addition to operating at highest frequency, this unit consumes the most of the power in the system.

Obviously, this unit is of particular focus to reduce power consumption. PLL with multiple outputs means to VCO with multiple output. Voltage Controlled Oscillator required for PLL should possess following characteristics.

- 1) The oscillating frequency should be restricted to the required bandwidth. For example, in European mobile phone applications, the VCO frequency should be varying between low= 1700 MHz and High=1800 MHz [3].
- 2) Due to process variations, the VCO frequency range should be extended to f_{min} , f_{max} , typically 10% higher and lower than the request range.
- 3) When the control voltage V_c is equal to $V_{DD}/2$, the clock should be centered in the middle of the desired frequency range.
- 4) The duty cycle of VCO clock output should be as close as possible to 50%. If this is not the case, the PLL would have problems locking, or would not produce a stable output clock [3].

A. High Performance VCO

The proposed PLL uses high performance VCO as shown in fig-3. It provides very good linearity. The principle of this VCO is a delay cell with linear delay dependence on the control voltage. The delay cell consists of a p-channel MOS (pmos) in series, controlled by $V_{control}$, and a pull-down n-channel MOS (nmos) controlled by V_{plage} . The delay dependence on $V_{control}$ is almost linear for the fall edge. The key point is to design an inverter just after the delay-cell with a very low commutation point V_c . The rise edge is almost unchanged [3].

The delay cells are connected, to delay both rise and fall edge of the oscillator as shown in following figure-3.

Fig. 3 High performance VCO

B. Multiple Outputs PLL

For multiple output PLL, 1x is the basic output of PLL, the 90° phase shifted output is generated using delay circuits or using logic circuits which in turn offers his speed performance at low power. It have multiple outputs 1x, 2x, 4x and 8x, which can be utilized in multiphase clocking circuits.

Figure-5 shows the block schematic of multiple output (four output) PLL with high performance VCO.

To achieve the proposed target fallowing steps are include in the design and analysis of proposed PLL.

Fig. 4 Block of Dregister (DFF)

- 1) Schematic design of each block of proposed PLL using CMOS transistors.
- 2) Performance verification of the above for different parameters.
- 3) CMOS layout for the proposed PLL using Lamda defined rules of VLSI backend3.1 software.

- 4) Verification of CMOS layout and parameter testing.
- 5) If the goal is achieved for all proposed parameter including detail verification, sing off for the design analysis and design will be ready for IC making.
- 6) If detail verification of parameters would not completed then again fallow the first step with different methodology.

Fig. 5 Block schematic of PLL with four outputs

As a result of technology scaling, there are increased process variations of circuit parameters such as the transistor channel length and transistor threshold voltage. The increased process variations can have a significant effect on circuit performance and power variations also have an impact on how exactly a parallel system should be designed [4]. BSIM4 model of the transistor nmos and pmos is having the specifications as fallows:

N-MOS BSIM4:

low leakage

MODEL N1 NMOS LEVEL=14 VTHO=0.19

U0=0.020 TOXE= 3.5E-9 LINT=0.000U

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure.6 shows the optimum, high efficient chip design of low power PLL with four multiple output using 45nm VLSI technology. This layout design is implemented using 29 nmos along with 28 pmos BSIM4 transistors with optimum dimensions of transistors and metal connections following the lamda based rules of microwind 3.1 software. This phase locked loop give a four multiple output as PLL8x equal to 3.3GHz, PLL4x equal to 1.65, GHz PLL 2x equal to 0.825 GHz and PLL 1x equal to 0.412GHz..

TABLE II

ANALYSIS OF VOLTAGE VARIATION OF VDD ON FREQUENCY OF VCO OUTPUT PLL1X

VDD Volt	Freq. (GHz)
0.800V	0.416
0.900V	0.416
1.00V	0.416
1.10V	0.416
1.20V	0.416

TABLE III

ANALYSIS OF VOLTAGE VARIATION OF VDD ON FREQUENCY OF VCO OUTPUT PLL8X

VDD Volt	Freq. (GHz)
0.800V	3.306
0.900V	3.306
1.00V	3.306
1.10V	3.306
1.20V	3.306

Figure -7 shows the frequency versus time response of PLL with four multiple output. It shows that as control voltage Vc increases the frequency of PLL decreases.

Fig. 7 Frequencies vs. time response of proposed PLL

Fig. 8 Voltage vs. time wave forms of PLL with four multiple output

The PLL is locked at 3.3 GHz frequency. Figure-8 shows voltage versus time waveforms of PLL's outputs and inputs. When control voltage is reaches to 0.415 volt, PLL is locked to the frequency of 3.3 GHz. Multiple output of the PLL gives multiple frequencies of amplitude 1 volt.

Above table II & III shows that, though there is variation of supply V_{DD} from 0.8V to 1.2V, the output of PLL remained stable which proved the high stability of the PLL. From the parametric analysis of designed PLL the power dissipation measured by V_{DD} at 1V is found to be 0.211mw, which shows that power consumption is very low (Low power).

Thus the effort has been taken to design high efficient, optimum area chip for PLL with four outputs.

6. CONCLUSION

The proposed PLL is designed using 45 nm CMOS/VLSI technology with microwind 3.1. This PLL gives a four multiple outputs as PLL8x, PLL4x, PLL2x and PLL1x simultaneously. This can be used for multichanneling communication system which in turn provides a very fast multitasking communication. This layout design is implemented using 29 nmos along with 28 pmos BSIM4 transistors. Though there is the variation of supply voltage V_{DD} from 0.8V to 1.2V, all the output of proposed PLL is found stable which proves the high stability of the PLL. From the parametric analysis of design tool, the power dissipation measured by V_{DD} at 1Volt is found 0.211miliwatt, which shows that power consumption is very low. In this way very high efficient, low power optimum area chip is designed for phase locked loop with four multiple outputs as PLL8x, PLL4x, and PLL2x & PLL1x of 3.3 GHz 1.65 GHz, 0.825 GHz, and 0.412 GHz respectively.

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